
ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORTS AS PREDICTORS OF TEACHERS' JOB SATISFACTION IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ENUGU STATE

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Abstract

The study investigated organizational supports as predictors of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 15,321 teachers in the 296 public secondary schools in Enugu State. The sample size for this study consisted of 1,532 teachers from 30 schools drawn using proportionate stratified sampling technique. The researcher developed questionnaires namely "Organizational Supports Scale (OSS)" and Teachers' Job Satisfaction Scale (TJSS)" were used for data collection. The face validation of the instruments was determined by three experts of which two were from the Department of Educational Management and Policy, and one in Measurement and Evaluation Unit in the Department of Educational Foundations, all from Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Cronbach alpha method was used to determine the internal consistencies of the instruments which yielded reliability coefficients of 0.81 and 0.80 for two Clusters of OSS and 0.81 was obtained for TJSS. The researcher together with five research assistants collected data for the study using the direct approach method and 98% return was recorded. Simple regression was used to answer the research questions and test hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed among others that staff professional development programme is a strong and significant predictor of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State. It was also found that mentorship programme is a moderate and significant predictor of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Ministry of Education should organize annual professional development programme for teachers to update their skills and improve their job satisfaction.

Keywords: Organizational Supports, Teachers, Job Satisfaction, Professional Development, Mentorship

Introduction

Education is a powerful tool for equipping individuals with requisite skills and knowledge to enable them function well in the society. It is also an instrument for inculcating the right values and attitudes in individuals to make them responsible and useful members of the society in which they belong. In Nigeria, the educational system is organized into different levels among them is secondary education.

Secondary education is a crucial phase of formal learning that advance the foundational knowledge acquired by learners in basic stage of education. Ugwu and Okoye (2024) opined that secondary education is considered as a strategic sub-sector of the education industry because it is at this level that the youths consolidate the basic knowledge gained in primary school, and also acquire the necessary culture to become useful citizens in the society. Secondary education exposes students to diverse subjects and vocational training to help them acquire practical skills and essential knowledge to prepare for work-life, future careers and more advanced academic pursuits in higher institutions of learning. Okafor, Nnebedum and Nwanne (2025) noted that secondary school education offers learning programmes that equip students with productive skills to engage in economic activities, essential knowledge for further studies and also help them fulfil the academic requirement needed for admission into higher institutions of learning. Operationally, secondary education is a learning programmes that takes place after basic stage of education to equip students with essential skills and knowledge for personal development, further their studies in higher institutions and also make substantial contributions to progress of the society. The daily activities of secondary school are planned, organized and controlled by a principal.

Principal is the chief administrator in charge of piloting the day-to-day affairs and operations of a secondary school. Okafor, Nnebedum and Oshia (2025) described a principal as administrate head who plans and oversees the implementation of school programmes. The principal is responsible for planning and executing policies, programmes, curricular and co-curricular activities in a secondary school. Also, principal is the custodian and manager of the available fund, time and facilities to ensure smooth functioning of activities of a secondary school for attainment of predetermined goals and objectives. Madubueze and Nwankwo (2024) noted that principal is the chief executive officer in charge of planning, overseeing and ensuring smooth operations of daily activities of a secondary school for attainment of predetermined objectives. Madubueze and Nwankwo added that principal is the manager entrusted with the task of fostering goal attainment through coordination of efforts of others. Contextually, principal is the administrative head who plans and oversees the daily activities of a secondary school to attain predetermined educational goals and objectives. It is the duty of the principal as human resource manager to render assistance and show concern towards the well-being of teachers through organizational supports.

Organizational supports are concerned with showing care and assisting members of staff to satisfy their needs in the workplace. Wang and Zhou (2022) described organizational supports as the act of showing concern for the well-being of staff to improve their job security and general contentment. Organizational supports are the acts of ensuring that members of staff receive adequate attention, provided with essential information and fairly treated in the workplace. It is the responsibility of principals to ensure that teachers are provided with the necessary supports to motivate them in carrying out their duties in secondary schools. Khalid (2023) defined

organizational supports as the way in which workers perceive the degree to which their employers value their involvement and well-being. Organizational supports are demonstrated through showing concern towards the problems of teachers, exchanging ideas and making suggestions to help them perform their duties in the workplace. Operationally, organizational supports are policies, programmes and system that accommodate the needs and interests of staff in the workplace. There is therefore need for the provision of organizational supports for teachers.

Teachers who are provided with the necessary supports are more likely to exhibit positive attitude to work. Khalid (2023) maintained that organizations with strong support for staff are more appealing to work for and workers are less likely to seek out for other jobs since they are fully valued, engaged and satisfied. Teachers could be supported in several ways. Nnebedum, Amobi, and Obionu (2024) noted that organizational supports could be in form of organizing staff professional development programmes, providing clear communication system, prioritizing well-being, making available mentorship opportunities and showing empathy to members of staff. Also, Salau (2022) outlined organizational supports to include: professional development opportunities, incentive system, promotion and other fringe benefits. The focus of this study is on professional development programmes and mentorship programmes. The justification for the two areas is because despite that they are very vital for daily activities of teachers, it seems that those aspects of organizational supports are yet to receive substantial attention.

Staff development programmes are learning opportunities provided for staff to update their knowledge and skills to enable them effectively carry out their duties. Staff professional development programmes include conference, workshop, symposium, orientation, exhibition, seminars and distance learning. Ali (2023) pointed out that professional development programmes can take many different forms, including apprenticeship, job shadowing, internships, and workforce diversity, role-playing, meetings, seminars, lectures, team-building activities, and simulation. Professional development programmes are capacity building platforms made available for teachers to improve their knowledge and skills of carrying out their duties in secondary schools. The notion of professional development programmes is to provide continuous learning opportunities for teachers. Umeh and Ogbuabor (2024) pointed out that the aims of staff professional development programmes are to improve pedagogical skills of teachers and keep them abreast with new curriculum reforms. Teachers do not only need professional development opportunities to stay up-to-date on trending practices in teaching profession but also mentorship programmes.

Mentoring programmes is a one-on-one relationship between a skilled, experienced persons (mentors) and a novice or inexperienced persons (mentees) to expose them to means of effectively discharging of their duties. Balinda (2023) averred that mentors provide encouragement and constructive feedback that helps mentees build their confidence, skills and decision-making abilities. Balinda added that through mentorship programmes, members of staff could be able to navigate their career paths more effectively, gain confidence and self-efficacy, develop leadership skills, and find fulfillment in their work. Mentoring programmes are learning activities in which more-experienced teachers share experience and knowledge to junior colleagues to improve the ways of performing tasks in secondary schools. Mentors tend to recommend their mentees for tasks, promotions, or other crucial activities in secondary schools which could make them feel fulfilled with their job. Bassey and Otu (2018) opined that a mentor teacher leads, guides and advises junior colleagues in a work situation characterized by mutual

trust and respect. Mentoring programmes provide opportunities for rendering advice and disseminating information on how things are to be carried to achieve desirable results. Mentorship programme could create healthy atmosphere that might contribute to teachers' job satisfaction.

Teachers' job satisfaction is an enjoyable or positive emotional state towards teaching activities caused by work conditions or experience. Teachers' job satisfaction is a feeling of contentment that members of teaching staff have and display towards their work conditions. Kurt and Duyar (2023) described teachers' job satisfaction as a pleasing or positive emotional state that emerges as a result of members of teaching staff evaluation of their work experiences. Teachers' job satisfaction is the situation in which academic staff experience a state of positive emotion from an assessment of their work. As defined by Amadi, Nte and Ugbe (2019), teachers' job satisfaction is a subjective feeling of fulfilment which teaching staff derive from working in a school. Furthermore, Amadi et al maintained that this feeling is subjective because it is entirely based on how teaching staff perceive that his experience and incentives derived from working for an organization have led to the fulfilment of his needs. If teachers perceive that their needs are fulfilled and their work experience is pleasant, they are likely to be satisfied with their job. Contextually, teachers' job satisfaction is the psychological feeling of contentment and happiness that members of teaching staff derived from work conditions, roles and demands.

Teachers' job satisfaction is determined through evaluation of various aspects of work roles, condition, environment and activities. Imasuen and Modupe (2022) noted that teachers' job satisfaction could be assessed through pay, promotion, recognition, job involvement, condition of work, policy, and administration, interpersonal relationship and relationship with supervisors and school size among others. Similarly, Lamaro and Okello (2024) maintained that teachers' job satisfaction could be assessed through supervisory support, recognition, financial remuneration, decision-making, delegation, conducive work environment, work security and relationship with co-workers and students. Teachers' job satisfaction could be assessed through promotion opportunities, salaries, workload, school administrators' attitudes toward teachers and colleagues, available facilities, communication system and feelings about the teaching profession.

Teachers who are satisfied with their job are more likely to remain in the teaching profession, come to class regularly, cover their scheme of work and put extra efforts to improve the academic achievement of students. Sinoy (2024) noted that teachers who are satisfied in their jobs bring excitement and dedication to class, are more engaged and productive, while dissatisfied teachers are unmotivated, feel burnout and become less productive which leads to low quality of instruction. Bahtilla and Hui (2021) noted that teachers' dissatisfaction can result in a lack of interest in teaching, leading to non-coverage of the syllabus, high failure rate, school drop-out, delinquency, and deviant behaviour in schools.

Some teachers who tend to be dissatisfied with their job possibly exhibit negative work attitude in public secondary schools in Enugu State. Agu and Manafa (2021) posited that some teachers tend to feel dissatisfied which they display by preferring to teach in extra moral classes than the normal school lesson, shy away from their duties, prefer to do other businesses than their teaching job and coming late to secondary schools in Enugu State, Nigeria. One is suspecting that teachers display job satisfaction possibly due to most of their needs are neglected in public secondary schools in Enugu State. Anukaenyi, Agusiobo and Ike (2024) noted that some principals fail to encourage staff to participate in decision-making process and are negligent of

their duty of communicating with members of staff which has contributed to misunderstandings, unrest and negative attitudes from teachers in public secondary schools in Enugu State, Nigeria. Also, Okigbo (2020) maintained that some principals show little or no interest towards staff welfare services and professional development which has dampened the morale of teachers and other workers in public secondary schools in Enugu State, Nigeria. Some teachers appear to be uncomfortable with their work conditions.

The work conditions and experiences of some teachers seem to be unfavourable in public secondary schools in Enugu State. Ogbuabor, Ebeh and Ezeilo (2022) asserted that teachers are working under difficult conditions as they found themselves in poor school environment with minimal supports, poor welfare packages and motivation, poor or inadequate communication, as well as unfairly rewarded for outstanding performance in public secondary schools in Enugu State. Agu and Manafa (2021) noted that some of the staff rooms are unconducive, there is lack of teaching materials, at times salaries are not promptly paid and some principals are autocratic among others. Also, Chukwueze and Chima (2024) maintained that teachers are poorly rewarded, rarely exposed to in-service training, decision making, recognition and newly recruited staff seem to be improperly guided by senior colleagues in public secondary schools in Enugu State. Continuing, Chukwueze and Chima (2024) asserted that due to poor/unsatisfactory treatment, some teachers are found to be nonchalant in the discharge of their duties which give rise to the graduation of poorly trained students who are found roaming the streets of Enugu State with some engaging in other social vices which grossly affect the development of the State. It is this backdrop that prompted the investigation into organizational supports as predictors of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Statement of the Problem

The roles of teachers towards attainment of educational goals in secondary schools cannot be over-emphasized. This is because teachers are responsible for translating and implementing curricular and co-curricular programmes in secondary schools. The skills and knowledge to be acquired by students perhaps depend on the level of commitment, satisfaction and job performance of teachers. Teachers tend to receive minimal supports as it seems that there is low motivation, poor communication and inadequate mentorship of newly recruited teachers in public secondary schools in Enugu State. It is noticeable that there are irregular in-service training opportunities which make some teachers fall short of skills to effectively perform their job.

Some newly recruited staff tend to be rarely assigned by experienced colleagues to guide and help them adjust to the work environment of public secondary schools in Enugu State. Teachers who perceived to be inadequately supported in discharging duties could feel dissatisfied with their work conditions and experiences which is bound to lower their morale and productivity. Teachers' dissatisfaction possibly account for lateness to work, absenteeism and lack of interest in teaching which tend to contribute to non-coverage of the syllabus at the due date and low performance in public secondary schools in Enugu State. Students and the society probably suffer from laxities in work attitude and job satisfaction of teachers. It is likely associated with high academic failure rate and deviant behaviour among students and shortages of skilled manpower to contribute to the development of Enugu State. To this effect, the researcher embarked on this research study to investigate organizational supports as predictors of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to determine organizational supports as predictors of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. Staff professional development programmes as predictors of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State.
2. Mentorship programmes as predictors of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the predictive value of staff professional development programmes on teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State?
2. What is the predictive value of mentorship programmes on teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Staff professional development programmes is not a significant predictor of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State.
2. Mentorship programme is not a significant predictor of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Methods

Correlational research design was adopted for this study. The study was carried out in Enugu State which is located in South-East Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. The choice of the area for the study was informed by the fact that teachers seem not to be fully supported in discharging their duties. The population of the study comprised 15,321 teachers in the 296 public secondary schools in Enugu State. The sample size for this study consist of 1,532 teachers from 30 schools drawn using proportionate stratified sampling technique.

The researcher-developed instruments titled "Organizational Supports Scale (OSS)" and Teachers' Job Satisfaction Scale (TJSS)" were used for data collection. The instruments were developed by the researchers based on literature review and consultation of experts in educational management. OSS contains 18 items arranged into two clusters namely A, B, C and D containing 10 and 8 items on staff professional development and mentorship programmes respectively. TJSS contained a total of 20 items which intends to elicit information on teachers' job satisfaction. The two sets of instruments were all structured on a four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The face validation of the instrument was determined. To ascertain this, the researcher presented the title, purpose of the study, research questions, hypotheses and copies of the questionnaire to three lecturers, two from the Department of Educational Management and Policy and one in Measurement and Evaluation from the Department of Educational Foundations, all in the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University. The observation and suggestions made by the experts were incorporated in the final draft to improve the quality of the instruments. The validation reports are attached as Appendix E on page 127. The internal consistencies of the instruments were determined by using Cronbach's alpha method which

yielded coefficient values of 0.81 and 0.80, for Clusters A and B of OSS with overall reliability coefficient value of 0.81. The reliability coefficient obtained for TJSS was 0.81.

The researcher and the research assistants who are secondary school teachers in Enugu State collected data for the study. A total of 1,532 copies of the instruments were distributed and 1504 copies of questionnaires were properly filled and successfully retrieved, indicating 98 percent return rate. The copies of the instruments distributed, properly filled and successfully retrieved were used for data analysis. Data were analyzed using simple regression to answer research questions, and test hypotheses. For the research questions the coefficient r and the size of the relationship was interpreted using the correlation coefficient by Senthilnathan (2019), as follows

Coefficient	Correlation
.00- .19	Very weak correlation
.20- .35	Weak correlation
.36- .50	Moderate correlation
.51- .70	Strong correlation
-.71- .99	Very strong correlation
1	Perfect

For decision on the hypotheses, where p -value was equal to or less than level of significant value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected but where p -value was greater than level of significant value of 0.05, the null hypotheses was not rejected.

Result

Research Question 1: What is the predictive value of professional development programmes on teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State?

Table 1: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on Professional Development Programmes as a Predictor of Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Secondary Schools

Model	N	r	r Square	Adjusted r Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
Professional Development Programme	1504	.673	.452	.452	.57701	Strong

As shown on Table 1, the predictive value of professional development programmes on teachers' job satisfaction is 0.673 with a coefficient of determination of 0.452. This shows that professional development programmes made 45.2% contributions to teachers' job satisfaction. The regression coefficient r of 0.673 indicated that professional development programme is a strong predictor of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Hypothesis One: Staff professional development programmes is not a significant predictors of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Table 2: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on Staff Professional Development Programmes as a Significant Predictor of Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Secondary Schools

Predictor	n	r	r ²	F	P-value	Remark
Professional Development Programmes	1504	.673	.452	1240.240	.000	*S

*Significant

Table 2 indicated that the simple regression coefficient (r) which is the predictive value of professional development programmes on teachers' job satisfaction is 0.673, while the r² is 0.452. This shows that professional development programmes could explain 45.2% changes in teachers' job satisfaction. The $F(1/1504) = 1240.240$ and the p -value of 0.000 are less than 0.05. Therefore, since the p -value is less than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, staff professional development programmes is a significant predictors of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Research Question 2: What is the predictive value of mentorship programmes on teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State?

Table 3: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on Mentorship Programmes as a Predictor of Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Secondary Schools

Model	n	R	r Square	Adjusted r Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Remarks
Mentorship Programme	1504	.457	.209	.208	.69348	Moderate

Table 3 reveals that the predictive value of mentorship programmes on teachers' job satisfaction is 0.457 with a coefficient of determination of 0.209 indicating that 20.9% change in teachers' job satisfaction could be explained by mentorship programme. The regression coefficient r of 0.457 indicated that mentorship programmes is a moderate predictor of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Hypothesis Two: Mentorship programmes is not a significant predictors of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Table 4: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis on Mentorship Programmes as a Significant Predictor of Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Secondary Schools

Predictor	n	R	r ²	F	P-value	Remark
Mentorship Programmes	1504	.457	.209	396.466	.000	*S

*Significant

It is indicated in Table 4 that the simple regression coefficient (r) which is the predictive value between mentorship programmes on teachers' job satisfaction is 0.457, while the r² is 0.209. This shows that 20.9% changes in teachers' job satisfaction could be attributed to mentorship programme. The $F(1/1504) = 396.466$ and the p -value of 0.000 are less than 0.05. Therefore,

since the p -value is less than the stipulated 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, mentorship programme is a significant predictors of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of the study revealed that professional development programme is a strong predictor of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State. This agreed with the finding of Chaudhary and Bhaskar (2016) which indicated that there was a strong correlation between professional development and job satisfaction of teaching staff. This also supported the finding of Pranathi and Saxena (2021) which revealed that there was a strong relationship between professional development and job satisfaction among teachers in public secondary schools. The above finding however disagreed with that of Srivastava and Gupta (2025) which showed that there was a weak relationship between professional development and job satisfaction among secondary school teachers. The difference in geographical location which is associated vary different educational policies and cultural context that influence professional development and teachers' job satisfaction. The possible explanation for this finding is that professional development programme equip teachers with skills to effectively discharge their duties which can account for the strong predictor of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State. Professional development programmes is strongly associated with teachers' job satisfaction probably due to the fact that it opens doors for career advancement and promotion.

Further result indicated that professional development programme is a significant predictor of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State. This affirmed the finding of Chaudhary and Bhaskar (2016) which indicated that there was a significant correlation between professional development and job satisfaction of teaching staff. This also gave credence to the finding of Pranathi and Saxena (2021) which revealed that there was a significant relationship between professional development and job satisfaction among teachers in public secondary schools. The above findings are not in tandum with Srivastava and Gupta (2025) which showed that there was insignificant relationship between professional development and job satisfaction among secondary school teachers. Professional development programme significantly predict teachers' job satisfaction through boosting their work-related knowledge and confidence to make them competent in performing their duties in public secondary schools in Enugu State.

The result of the study revealed that mentorship programme is a moderate predictor of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State. This is in line with the finding of Botha and Hugo (2021) which showed that mentoring programme had a moderate relationship with teachers' job satisfaction. The agreement between the findings is associated with the fact that the studies were conducted in secondary level of education using teachers as the participants. This contradicted the finding of Lee and Montiel (2011) which showed that mentorship programme had strong correlation with job satisfaction of mental health professionals. The contradiction between the findings could be explained by difference in time span of 14 years that could lead to changes in research findings. The finding is plausible due to the fact the mentorship programme is associated with pairing teachers with experienced colleagues to expand their knowledge of carrying out teaching activities and accelerate their career advancement. Mentorship programmes moderately predict teachers' job satisfaction as it

is associated with culture of collaboration and sharing experience of effective ways of performing tasks in public secondary schools in Enugu State. It is through mentorship programme that teachers receive guidance and assistance that moderately contribute to their job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Further result indicated that mentorship programme is a significant predictor of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State. This upheld the finding of Botha and Hugo (2021) which indicated that mentoring programme had a significant relationship with teachers' job satisfaction. The agreement between the findings might be connected to similarity in mentorship programme at secondary level of education. The finding could be explained by the fact the mentorship programme is associated pairing staff which help them to develop close bonds, mutual respect and trust that ultimately contribute to the significant predictor of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that organizational supports are strong and significant predictors of teachers' job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State. Teachers who are supported through professional development and mentorship programmes feel valued which motivate and increase their job satisfaction in public secondary schools in Enugu State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Ministry of Education in Enugu State should organize annual professional development programme for teachers to update their skills and improve their job satisfaction.
2. Principals in Enugu State should establish clear guidelines that state frequency of meetings, expectations and duration to ensure a structured mentorship programme that can enhance teachers' job satisfaction.

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